

Synthesis, molecular docking, and anti-inflammatory evaluation of novel 4-(benzo[*d*][1,3]dioxol-5-yloxy)-*N,N*-2-yn-1-amine derivatives as potent cysteinyl leukotriene receptor (CysLT2) antagonists

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Abstract

Cysteinyl leukotrienes (CysLTs), derived from arachidonic acid, play a crucial role in regulating inflammation. We synthesized a novel series of CysLT2 antagonists containing the benzo[*d*][1,3]dioxole moiety using a synthetic strategy based on the Mannich reaction, resulting in the formation of 4-(benzo[*d*][1,3]dioxol-5-yloxy)-*N,N*-2-yn-1-amine. The structures of the synthesized compounds were characterized through NMR and HRMS analyses, and a plausible reaction mechanism was proposed. The inhibitory activities of all new compounds against CysLT2 were evaluated *in vitro*. Among them, compounds **4d** and **4g** exhibited the most potent inhibitory effects, with IC₅₀ values of 18.7 μM and 15.5 μM, respectively. These findings were further supported by molecular docking studies, which highlighted the binding interactions of these compounds within the kinase's active site.

Graphical abstract:**Keywords**

sesamol, leukotrienes, inflammation, CysLT, Mannich reaction, allergy, asthma

Introduction

Lipid mediators called cysteinyl leukotrienes (CysLTs) are produced from arachidonic acid and are essential for the regulation of inflammation, especially in allergy and respiratory diseases. CysLTs have a major role in the development of asthma, allergic rhinitis, and other inflammatory illnesses since they are mainly responsible for bronchoconstriction, increased vascular permeability, and immune cell recruitment (Gusach et al. 2019; Sood et al. 2024). CysLTs work through certain receptors, and one of the main targets of therapeutic interventions is the CysLT2 receptor (CysLT2R). A number of intracellular signaling pathways, including those regulated by protein kinase C and phospholipase C, are connected to the CysLT2R, which causes a variety of physiological reactions that worsen bronchoconstriction and inflammation (Gelosa et al. 2017). CysLT2 receptor antagonists have become a viable treatment option for inflammatory disorders. By inhibiting CysLTs at the receptor level, these antagonists hope to lessen the pro-inflammatory effects of the protein.

According to preliminary research, CysLT2 antagonists may offer therapeutic advantages over standard CysLT1 antagonists, especially in situations where CysLT2R activation plays a major role in the pathophysiology of the disease (Sekioka et al. 2015; Zhou et al. 2022). The field of CysLT2 antagonist research is still developing, with studies being conducted to learn more about the drugs' safety profiles, efficacy, and possible use in combination therapy. In the larger context of focusing on leukotriene signaling pathways to reduce inflammation and enhance outcomes in patients with respiratory and allergy disorders, this introduction emphasizes the importance of CysLT2 antagonists (Jo-Watanabe et al. 2019; Voisin et al. 2021).

Additionally, sesamol (benzo[*d*][1,3]dioxol-5-ol), a naturally occurring antioxidant present in sesame seeds, provides anti-inflammatory properties (Majdalawieh and Mansour 2019). Sesamol is a phenolic substance with a strong antioxidant capacity, and its chemical formula is $C_7H_6O_3$. It has anti-inflammatory, anticancer, cardioprotective, and neuroprotective properties in addition to being useful in the preservation of food, cosmetics, and

medications (Jayaraj et al. 2020; Kushwaha et al. 2020; Assab et al. 2024; Dayyih et al. 2024). Sesamol shields cells against oxidative stress, a factor in the emergence of chronic illnesses (Ren et al. 2018). Because both strategies concentrate on reducing the impacts of oxidative stress and inflammation, sesamol qualities complement the current research being done on CysLT2 antagonists as a means of regulating inflammation.

As part of our continuous interest in the design and discovery of new biologically active compounds (Jaber et al. 2020; Al-Mahadeen et al. 2022; Al-Mahadeen and Jaber 2024; Al-Mahadeen et al. 2024a; Al-Mahadeen et al. 2024c; Al-Mahadeen et al. 2024d; Jaber et al. 2024; Al-Mahadeen et al. 2025), we became interested in generating hybrid adducts composed of sesamol and different secondary aliphatic amines as potential lipid mediators called cysteinyl leukotrienes (CysLTs) antagonists. The synthesis of 4-(benzo[*d*][1,3]dioxol-5-yloxy)-*N,N*-2-yn-1-amine pharmacophore was achieved *via* copper-catalyzed Mannich reaction (Lu et al. 2019; Jaber et al. 2022; Jaber et al. 2023a; Jaber et al. 2023b; Al-Mahadeen et al. 2024b) (as in Scheme 1).

In silico profiling against several targets suggested the new compounds bind and inhibit the CysLTs antagonist (Parravicini et al. 2010; Sadybekov et al. 2020) and were therefore evaluated in vitro as CysLTs antagonists. Two of them displayed μM IC_{50} values. Interestingly, there are no previous studies on the synthesis and biological properties of these derivatives.

Materials and methods

Experimental part

Benzo[*d*][1,3]dioxol-5-ol, propargyl bromide, formaldehyde, dimethylamine, diethylamine, dipropylamine, dibutylamine, 1-methylpiperazine, 1-ethylpiperazine, 1-(3-chlorophenyl)piperazine, morpholine, 1-(2-pyridinyl)piperazine, and 2-(1-piperazinyl)pyrimidine were obtained from Acros, BLD Pharma, and Sigma-Aldrich. Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance III 500 MHz spectrometer, using trimethylsilane (TMS) as the internal standard. Chemical shifts (δ -values) were reported in parts per million (ppm), and DEPT experiments were performed to determine the carbon atom multiplicities. High-resolution mass spectra (HRMS) were acquired using a Bruker APEX IV 7 Tesla instrument, employing the electrospray ionization (ESI) technique with collision-induced dissociation. Solvents used in the study were sourced from Aldrich and BLD Pharma.

Chemistry

Synthesis and characterization of compounds (3-4a-j)

Synthesis of 5-(prop-2-yn-1-yloxy)benzo[*d*][1,3]dioxole (3)

This compound was prepared by the reaction of benzo[*d*][1,3]dioxol-5-ol **1** with propargyl bromide **2** in the presence of potassium carbonate in dimethylformamide according to a recently reported procedure (Chen et al. 2015).

General procedure for synthesis of compounds (4a-j)

4-(benzo[*d*][1,3]dioxol-5-yloxy)-*N,N*-2-yn-1-amine (4a-j)

A stirred solution of aqueous formaldehyde (35%, 1 mL) and CuI (25 mg) in 2 mL of DMSO was prepared. Alkyne **3** (0.60 mmol, 1 eq) and the appropriate amine (0.72 mmol, 1.2 eq) were then added to the solution. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 3 hours. Afterward, 8 mL of water was added, and the mixture was extracted with ethyl acetate (2 × 25 mL). The resulting residue was purified by column chromatography using a mixture of n-hexane and ethyl acetate (2:8, v/v) as the eluent to obtain compounds **4a-j**.

(benzo[*d*][1,3]dioxol-5-yloxy)-*N,N*-dimethylbut-2-yn-1-amine (4a)

Figure 1.

Light brown oil (0.0301 g, 75% yield). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , in ppm): 2.64 (s, 6H, $-\text{CH}_3$), 3.37 (s, 2H, $-\text{CH}_2\text{N}$), 4.59 (s, 2H, $-\text{OCH}_2$), 5.85 (s, 2H, H-2), 6.35, 6.37 (dd, 1H, $J = 1.5$ Hz, H-6), 6.52 (s, 1H, H-4), 6.65 (d, 1H, $J = 8.5$ Hz, H-7). $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3 , in ppm): 42.1 (2C, $-\text{CH}_3$), 48.2 (1C, $-\text{CH}_2\text{N}$), 57.2 (1C, OCH_2), 79.5, 82.9 (2C, alkyne-C), 98.8 (1C, C-4), 101.2 (1C, C-2), 106.7 (1C, C-6), 107.8 (1C, C-7), 142.1 (1C, C-7a), 148.2 (1C, C-3a), 153.1 (1C, C-5). HRMS (ESI) m/z = calculated for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{NO}_3$, $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: 234.11297, found 234.11131.

4-(benzo[*d*][1,3]dioxol-5-yloxy)-*N,N*-diethylbut-2-yn-1-amine (4b)

Figure 2.

Light brown oil (0.0326 g, 71% yield). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , in ppm): 1.93 (t, 6H, $J=7.5$ Hz, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.32 (t, 4H, $J=7.5$ Hz, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 3.37 (s, 2H, $-\text{CH}_2\text{N}$), 4.59 (s, 2H, $-\text{OCH}_2$), 5.85 (s, 2H, H-2), 6.35, 6.37 (dd, 1H, $J=1.5$ Hz, H-6), 6.52 (s, 1H, H-4), 6.65 (d, 1H, $J=8.5$ Hz, H-7). $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3 , in ppm): 12.9 (2C, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 42.1 (1C, $-\text{CH}_2\text{N}$), 49.7 (2C, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 57.2 (1C, OCH_2), 79.5, 82.9 (2C, alkyne-C), 98.8 (1C, C-4), 101.2 (1C, C-2), 106.7 (1C, C-6), 107.8 (1C, C-7), 142.1 (1C, C-7a), 148.2 (1C, C-3a), 153.1 (1C, C-5). HRMS (ESI) m/z = calculated for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{20}\text{NO}_3$, $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: 263.11062, found 263.11082.

4-(benzo[d][1,3]dioxol-5-yloxy)-*N,N*-dipropylbut-2-yn-1-amine (4c)

Figure 3.

Light brown oil (0.0299 g, 72% yield). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , in ppm): 0.82 (t, 6H, $J=7.3$ Hz, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 1.39 (sextet, 4H, $J=7.4$ Hz, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.32 (t, 4H, $J=7.5$ Hz, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 3.37 (s, 2H, $-\text{CH}_2\text{N}$), 4.59 (s, 2H, $-\text{OCH}_2$), 5.85 (s, 2H, H-2), 6.35, 6.37 (dd, 1H, $J=1.5$ Hz, H-6), 6.52 (s, 1H, H-4), 6.65 (d, 1H, $J=8.5$ Hz, H-7). $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3 , in ppm): 11.9 (2C, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 20.7 (2C, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 42.1 (1C, $-\text{CH}_2\text{N}$), 55.7 (1C, OCH_2), 57.2 (2C, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 79.5, 82.9 (2C, alkyne-C), 98.7 (1C, C-4), 101.2 (1C, C-2), 106.7 (1C, C-6), 107.8 (1C, C-7), 142.1 (1C, C-7a), 148.2 (1C, C-3a), 153.1 (1C, C-5). HRMS (ESI) m/z = calculated for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{24}\text{NO}_3$, $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: 290.17507, found 290.17485.

4-(benzo[d][1,3]dioxol-5-yloxy)-*N,N*-dibutylbut-2-yn-1-amine (4d)

Figure 4.

Light brown oil (0.0298 g, 62% yield). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , in ppm): 0.85 (t, 6H, $J=7.3$ Hz, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 1.24 (sextet, 4H, $J=6.9$ Hz, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 1.35 (sextet, 4H, $J=7.4$ Hz, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.35 (t, 4H, $J=7.5$ Hz, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 3.37 (s, 2H, $-\text{CH}_2\text{N}$), 4.59 (s, 2H, $-\text{OCH}_2$), 5.85 (s, 2H, H-2), 6.35, 6.37 (dd, 1H, $J=1.5$ Hz, H-6), 6.51 (s, 1H, H-4), 6.64 (d, 1H, $J=8.5$ Hz, H-7).

$^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3 , in ppm): 14.0 (2C, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 20.6 (2C, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 29.7 (2C, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 42.1 (1C, $-\text{CH}_2\text{N}$), 53.5 (1C, OCH_2), 57.2 (2C, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 79.6, 82.9 (2C, alkyne-C), 98.7 (1C, C-4), 101.2 (1C, C-2), 106.6 (1C, C-6), 107.8 (1C, C-7), 142.1 (1C, C-7a), 148.2 (1C, C-3a), 153.1 (1C, C-5). HRMS (ESI) m/z = calculated for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{28}\text{NO}_3$, $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: 318.20637, found 218.20576.

1-(4-(benzo[d][1,3]dioxol-5-yloxy)but-2-yn-1-yl)-4-methylpiperazine (4e)

Figure 5.

Light brown oil (0.0329 g, 71% yield). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (500 MHz, DMSO, in ppm): 2.10 (s, 3H, $-\text{NCH}_3$), 2.35 (ps t, 4H, H-2'/H-6'), 3.23 (s, 2H, $-\text{CH}_2\text{N}$), 3.31 (ps t, 4H, H-3'/H-4'), 4.68 (s, 2H, $-\text{OCH}_2$), 5.51 (s, 2H, H-2), 6.35, 6.37 (dd, 1H, $J=1.8$ Hz, H-6), 6.61 (s, 1H, H-4), 6.76 (d, 1H, $J=8.5$ Hz, H-7). $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3 , in ppm): 46.1 (1C, $-\text{NCH}_3$), 46.6 (1C, $-\text{CH}_2\text{N}$), 51.5 (2C, C-2'/C-6'), 54.9 (2C, C-3'/C-5'), 57.0 (1C, OCH_2), 80.7, 83.3 (2C, alkyne-C), 98.8 (1C, C-4), 101.5 (1C, C-2), 107.0 (1C, C-6), 108.4 (1C, C-7), 142.0 (1C, C-7a), 148.3 (1C, C-3a), 153.1 (1C, C-5). HRMS (ESI) m/z = calculated for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$, $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: 288.15975, found 288.15908.

1-(4-(benzo[d][1,3]dioxol-5-yloxy)but-2-yn-1-yl)-4-ethylpiperazine (4f)

Figure 6.

Light brown oil (0.0211 g, 65% yield). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (500 MHz, DMSO, in ppm): 1.18 (ps t, 3H, $-\text{NCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.02 (t, 2H, $J=7.0$ Hz, $-\text{NCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.35 (ps t, 4H, H-2'/H-6'), 3.23 (s, 2H, $-\text{CH}_2\text{N}$), 3.31 (ps t, 4H, H-3'/H-4'), 4.68 (s, 2H, $-\text{OCH}_2$), 5.91 (s, 2H, H-2), 6.35, 6.37 (dd, 1H, $J=1.8$ Hz, H-6), 6.61 (s, 1H, H-4), 6.76 (d, 1H, $J=8.5$ Hz, H-7). $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3 , in ppm): 14.2 (1C, $-\text{NCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 45.9 (1C, $-\text{CH}_2\text{N}$), 47.1 (1C, $-\text{NCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 51.8 (2C, C-2'/C-6'), 54.9 (2C, C-3'/C-5'), 57.2 (1C, OCH_2), 80.1, 82.6 (2C, alkyne-C), 98.7 (1C, C-4), 101.2 (1C, C-2), 106.5 (1C, C-6), 107.9 (1C, C-7), 142.2 (1C, C-7a), 148.2 (1C,

C-3a), 153.1 (1C, C-5). HRMS (ESI) m/z = calculated for $C_{17}H_{23}N_2O_3$, $[M+Na]^+$: 325.15219, found 325.15169.

1-(4-(benzo[d][1,3]dioxol-5-yloxy)but-2-yn-1-yl)-4-(3-chlorophenyl)piperazine (4g)

Figure 7.

Light brown oil (0.0236 g, 69% yield). 1H NMR (500 MHz, $CDCl_3$, in ppm): 2.63 (t, 4H, $J = 4.5$ Hz, H-2'/H-6'), 3.16 (t, $J = 4.5$ Hz, 4H, H-3'/H-4'), 3.35 (s, 2H, $-CH_2N$), 4.61 (s, 2H, $-OCH_2$), 5.85 (s, 2H, H-2), 6.35, 6.37 (dd, 1H, $J = 1.2$ Hz, H-6), 6.52 (s, 1H, H-4), 6.66 (d, 1H, $J = 8.5$ Hz, H-7), 6.73 (d, 1H, $J = 8.3$ Hz, H-6''), 6.76 (d, 1H, $J = 8.0$ Hz, H-4''), 6.83 (s, 1H, H-2''), 7.12 (t, 2H, $J = 8.2$ Hz, H-5''). ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, $CDCl_3$, in ppm): 47.1 (1C, $-CH_2N$), 48.2 (2C, C-2'/C-6'), 51.7 (2C, C-3'/C-5'), 57.2 (1C, OCH_2), 80.5, 82.2 (2C, alkyne-C), 98.5 (1C, C-4), 101.2 (1C, C-2), 106.6 (1C, C-6), 107.9 (1C, C-7), 114.0 (1C, C-6''), 115.8 (1C, C-2''), 119.4 (1C, C-4''), 130.0 (1C-C-5''), 134.4 (1C, C-3''), 142.3 (1C, C-7a), 148.2 (1C, C-3a), 152.2 (1C, C-1''), 153.1 (1C, C-5). HRMS (ESI) m/z = calculated for $C_{21}H_{22}ClN_2O_3$, $[M+H]^+$: 385.13135, found 385.13300.

4-(4-(benzo[d][1,3]dioxol-5-yloxy)but-2-yn-1-yl)morpholine (4h)

Figure 8.

Light brown oil (0.0245 g, 69% yield). 1H NMR (500 MHz, $CDCl_3$, in ppm): 2.46 (ps t, 4H, H-2'/H-6'), 3.26 (s, 2H, $-CH_2N$), 3.66 (ps t, 4H, H-3'/H-4'), 4.58 (s, 2H, $-OCH_2$), 5.56 (s, 2H, H-2), 6.33, 6.35 (dd, 1H, $J = 1.2$ Hz, H-6), 6.50 (s, 1H, H-4), 6.64 (d, 1H, $J = 8.5$ Hz, H-7). ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, $CDCl_3$, in ppm): 47.4 (1C, $-CH_2N$), 52.3 (2C, C-2'/C-6'), 57.2 (2C, C-3'/C-5'), 66.8 (1C, OCH_2), 80.4, 82.3 (2C, alkyne-C), 98.7 (1C, C-4), 101.2 (1C, C-2), 106.5 (1C, C-6), 107.8 (1C, C-7), 142.2 (1C, C-7a), 148.2 (1C, C-3a), 153.1 (1C, C-5). HRMS (ESI) m/z = calculated for $C_{15}H_{18}NO_4$, $[M+H]^+$: 276.12303, found 276.12131.

1-(4-(benzo[d][1,3]dioxol-5-yloxy)but-2-yn-1-yl)-4-(pyridin-2-yl)piperazine (4i)

Figure 9.

Light brown oil (0.0255 g, 70% yield). 1H NMR (500 MHz, $CDCl_3$, in ppm): 2.60 (ps t, 4H, H-2'/H-6'), 3.35 (s, 2H, $-CH_2N$), 3.51 (ps t, 4H, H-3'/H-4'), 4.58 (s, 2H, $-OCH_2$), 5.83 (s, 2H, H-2), 6.33, 6.34 (dd, 1H, $J = 2.1$ Hz, H-6), 6.50 (s, 1H, H-4), 6.58 (ps t, 1H, H-7), 6.60 (br s, 1H, H-6''), 6.62 (ps t, 1H, H-4''), 7.41 (t, 1H, $J = 7.0$ Hz, H-5''), 8.13 (t, 1H, $J = 3.2$ Hz, H-3''). ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, $CDCl_3$, in ppm): 44.9 (2C, C-3'/C-5'), 47.1 (1C, $-CH_2N$), 51.6 (2C, C-2'/C-6'), 57.2 (1C, OCH_2), 80.6, 82.1 (2C, alkyne-C), 98.7 (1C, C-4), 101.2 (1C, C-2), 106.5 (1C, C-6), 107.2 (1C, C-7), 107.8 (1C, C-4''), 113.5 (1C, C-6''), 137.5 (1C, C-5''), 142.2 (1C, C-7a), 147.9 (1C, C-3''), 148.2 (1C, C-3a), 153.0 (1C, C-5), 159.3 (1C, C-1''). HRMS (ESI) m/z = calculated for $C_{20}H_{22}N_3O_3$, $[M+H]^+$: 352.16557, found 352.16380.

2-(4-(4-(benzo[d][1,3]dioxol-5-yloxy)but-2-yn-1-yl)piperazin-1-yl)pyrimidine (4j)

Figure 10.

Light brown oil (0.0300 g, 79% yield). 1H NMR (500 MHz, $CDCl_3$, in ppm): 2.52 (t, 4H, $J = 4.8$ Hz, H-2'/H-6'), 3.32 (s, 2H, $-CH_2N$), 3.78 (ps t, 4H, H-3'/H-4'), 4.55 (s, 2H, $-OCH_2$), 5.82 (s, 2H, H-2), 6.30, 6.31 (dd, 1H, $J = 2.1$ Hz, H-6), 6.41 (t, 1H, $J = 4.7$ Hz, H-4''), 6.47 (br s, 1H, H-4), 6.58 (d, 1H, $J = 8.5$ Hz, H-7), 8.13 (d, 2H, $J = 4.7$ Hz, H-3''/H-5''). ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, $CDCl_3$, in ppm): 43.3 (2C, C-3'/C-5'), 47.1 (1C, $-CH_2N$), 51.6 (2C, C-2'/C-6'), 57.1 (1C, OCH_2), 80.6, 82.1 (2C, alkyne-C), 98.7 (1C, C-4), 101.2 (1C, C-2), 106.5 (1C, C-6), 107.8 (1C, C-7), 109.9 (1C, C-4''), 142.2 (1C, C-7a), 148.2 (1C, C-3a), 152.9 (1C, C-5), 157.7 (2C, C-3''/C-5''), 161.1 (1C, C-1''). HRMS (ESI) m/z = calculated for $C_{19}H_{21}N_4O_3$, $[M+H]^+$: 353.16082, found 353.16102.

Biological evaluation

In vitro bioassay against cysteinyl leukotriene antagonists

CysLT2 – NFAT-bla CHO-K1: Agonist and antagonist screening protocols

Agonist screen

The bioassay followed the supplier's protocol using Invitrogen Z'-LYTE® CysLT2-NFAT-bla CHO-K1 cells. Thawed cells were resuspended in Assay Media (DMEM with 1% dialyzed FBS, 25 mM HEPES at pH 7.3, 0.1 mM NEAA, and 100 U/mL/100 µg/mL Pen/Strep) to a final concentration of 312,500 cells/mL. A volume of 32 µL (10,000 cells) was dispensed into each well of a 384-well TC-treated assay plate. The plate was incubated for 16–24 hours at 37 °C with 5% CO₂ in a humidified incubator.

Subsequently, 4 µL of a 10X serial dilution of LTD4 (control agonist, starting at 1,000 nM) or test compounds were added to the designated wells, with 4 µL of Assay Media added to bring the final volume to 40 µL per well. After a 5-hour incubation at 37 °C/5% CO₂ in a humidified incubator, 8 µL of a 1 µM Substrate + Solution D Loading Solution was added to each well. The plate was incubated at room temperature for 2 hours before fluorescence readings were taken using a plate reader.

Antagonist screen activated by LTD4

The antagonist screening utilized the same cell preparation and plating procedures as the agonist screen. Each well received 32 µL of the prepared cell suspension and was incubated for 16–24 hours at 37 °C with 5% CO₂ in a humidified incubator.

Next, 4 µL of 10X test compounds or assay media were added to the respective wells and pre-incubated with the cells for 30 minutes under the same conditions. Subsequently, 4 µL of a 10X solution of the control agonist LTD4, at its pre-determined EC80 concentration, was added to the wells containing either the control antagonist or test compounds. The plate was incubated for 5 hours at 37 °C/5% CO₂ in a humidified incubator.

Finally, 8 µL of a 1 µM substrate + solution D loading solution was added to each well, and the plate was incubated at room temperature for 2 hours. Fluorescence was measured using a plate reader. It is noted that the assay currently lacks a defined antagonist control.

Docking study

Molecular docking simulations were performed to assess the binding affinity of synthesized compounds **4d** and **4g** to the CysLT2 receptor (PDB ID: 6RZ6) (Gusach et al. 2019). The simulations were conducted using AutoDock 4.2.6 (Morris et al. 2009), following previously established protocols from our group (Al-Anazi et al. 2022; Sahar Jafal 2022). Protein preparation was carried out in BIOVIA® Discovery Studio® 16.1 (Dassault-Systèmes 2016), which involved removing water molecules and co-crystallized structures. The co-crystallized antagonist (Compound **11a**) (Gusach et al. 2019) (Fig. 11) was extracted from the crystal structure to serve as the control ligand.

AutoDockTools 1.5.6 (Morris et al. 2009) was used to prepare the protein by adding Kollman charges and polar hydrogens, while Gasteiger charges were applied to the optimized ligand structures. A grid box with dimensions

Figure 11. 2D Chemical structure of the co-crystallized antagonist (compound **11a**) from (PDB ID: 6RZ6). Generated by ChemDraw® software.

of 16.453 Å³ and coordinates set at -23.401 (x), 11.66 (y), and -20.827 (z) was defined. Docking simulations were executed using 100 runs of the Lamarckian genetic algorithm with default parameters.

Conformations with the lowest binding free energy (LEB) and the highest cluster populations were selected for further analysis. Interaction analyses were conducted using BIOVIA® Discovery Studio® 16.1 to explore ligand-receptor interactions.

Results and discussion

Chemistry

In this work, a number of 4-(benzo[*d*][1,3]dioxol-5-yloxy)-*N,N*-2-yn-1-amine compounds were synthesized and identified. Benzo[*d*][1,3]dioxol-5-ol **1** was first intended to be linked to the propargylic moiety. Initially, benzo[*d*][1,3]dioxol-5-ol **1** was treated with propargyl bromide (3-Bromoprop-1-yne) and sodium carbonate (Na₂CO₃) in acetonitrile to obtain 5-(prop-2-yn-1-yloxy) benzo[*d*][1,3]dioxole **3** in 90% yield after 4 hours (Chen et al. 2015). Compound **3** started the Mannich reaction, which resulted in the ten distinct compounds (**4a–j**) shown in Table 1. Briefly, a catalytic amount of cuprous iodide (CuI) in DMSO, formaldehyde, and amine (2° amine) was applied to compound **3**. Stirring the components for 4 hours at room temperature resulted in 65–79% yields of the necessary compounds (**4a–j**) (Scheme 1).

High-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) and ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectroscopy were used to characterize the novel compounds. The mass spectra were found to be in good agreement with estimated values and provided the right molecular ion peaks. The ¹H-NMR spectra revealed protons that corresponded to aliphatic amine protons and the OCH₂ moiety in the aliphatic region δ = 4.55–5.68 ppm. The singlet CH₂N protons appeared at about the region δ = 3.26–3.37 ppm, while the singlet H-2 protons appeared at about δ = 5.85 ppm. At δ = 6.35–6.65 ppm, all aromatic moieties displayed resonances. However, the ¹³C NMR spectra displayed all of the synthesized compounds' distinctive signals, including several aliphatic peaks for the C-2 and aliphatic amine moieties. In the aromatic area, all aromatic moieties displayed distinct and accurate carbon signals. For the majority of the synthesized compounds, the two alkyne carbon atom peaks (79.0–83.0) are identifiable.

Table 1. Structures of synthesized novel 4-(benzo[d][1,3]dioxol-5-yloxy)-*N,N*-2-yn-1-amine.

Compound	R1	Compound	R1
<i>4a</i>	-N(CH ₃) ₂	<i>4f</i>	
<i>4b</i>	-N(CH ₂ CH ₃) ₂	<i>4g</i>	
<i>4c</i>	-N((CH ₂) ₂ CH ₃) ₂	<i>4h</i>	
<i>4d</i>	-N((CH ₂) ₃ CH ₃) ₂	<i>4i</i>	
<i>4e</i>			

Molecular docking

This study investigated the potential of **4d** and **4g** compounds as antagonists for the CysLT₂ receptor. To validate the docking procedure, the co-crystal structure, compound **11a**, was redocked, yielding an RMSD value of 0.98 Å, as represented in Fig. 12. It is proposed that RMSD values falling beneath the 2 Å limit validate the reliability of the docking protocol for subsequent examinations (Hevener et al. 2009). Table 2 shows the predicted binding affinities of the two compounds (**4d**, **4g**) against the CysLT₂ receptor using molecular docking simulations.

Compound **4d** exhibited a binding energy of -6.57 kcal/mol, with an IC₅₀ value of 18.7 μM, indicating moderate binding affinity and inhibitory activity. In comparison, compound **4g** demonstrated a significantly lower binding energy of -8.50 kcal/mol and an IC₅₀ of 15.5 μM, reflecting a stronger interaction with the receptor. However, both compounds showed less potent binding energy and higher IC₅₀ values than the co-crystallized antagonist **11a**, which achieved a superior binding energy of -14.92 kcal/mol and an IC₅₀ of 2.9 nM. These results suggest that while compounds **4d** and **4g** interact effectively with the receptor, they are less potent than **11a**, likely due to differences in binding modes and interaction profiles.

Detailed interaction analysis revealed differences in the amino acids involved in the binding of each compound. Compound **4d** formed hydrophobic interactions with Tyr119, Met201, Ala205, His270, Leu271, and Arg267 (Fig. 14). However, no hydrogen bonds or electrostatic interactions were observed, which might contribute to its relatively lower binding energy and potency compared to **4g** and **11a**. Compound **4g** displayed a more diverse interaction profile, forming hydrogen bonds with Arg94 and Leu190 and hydrophobic interactions with Tyr119, Met172, Leu173, Leu188, Leu198, and Met201. This expanded interaction network likely accounts for its enhanced binding energy relative to **4d** (Fig. 14). Co-crystallized antagonist **11a** (Fig. 13) exhibited the most extensive interaction profile. It formed hydrogen bonds with Lys37 and Tyr119, electrostatic pi-cation interaction with Arg267, and hydrophobic contacts with Tyr123 (T-shape aromatic interaction), Leu190, Leu198, Met201, Ile204, Ala205, and Leu271. The comprehensive interaction network explains its superior binding affinity and IC₅₀ value.

The lower binding energy of **4g** compared to **4d** suggests that the additional hydrogen bonding and broader hydrophobic interaction network of **4g** play a critical role in enhancing its binding affinity. Conversely, the absence of hydrogen bonding and electrostatic interactions in **4d** limits its overall interaction strength, resulting in weaker binding. The

Scheme 1. Synthetic routes for the synthesis of 4-(benzo[*d*][1,3]dioxol-5-yloxy)-*N,N*-2-yn-1-amine pharmacophore hybrid.

Figure 12. Stick representations of co-crystal structure Compound **11a** (gray) color and the docked configurations (orange) against the CysLT2 receptor (PDB ID: 6RZ6). Generated by Biovia Discovery Studio Visualizer®.

Figure 13. Stick representation of co-crystal structure compound **11a** within the CysLT2 receptor (PDB ID: 6RZ6) binding site. Generated by Biovia Discovery Studio Visualizer®.

Table 2. Lowest binding energy scores (Kcal/mol) for the co-crystal antagonist and the synthesized compounds **4d** and **4g** against the CysLT2 receptor.

Compound	Lowest Binding Energy (LBE) Kcal/mol	Tested IC ₅₀	Interacting Amino Acids		
			H-Bond	Electrostatic	Hydrophobic
4d	-6.57	18.7 μM	ND	ND	Tyr119, Met201, Ala205, His270, Leu271, Arg267, Leu271
4g	-8.50	15.5 μM	Arg94, Leu190	ND	Tyr119, Met172, Leu173, Leu188, Leu198, Met201
11a (co-crystal structure)	-14.92	2.9 nM	Lys37, Tyr119	Arg267 (pi-cation)	Tyr123 (T-shape), Leu190, Leu198, Met201, Ile204, Ala205, leu271.

co-crystal antagonist **11a** remains the benchmark compound due to its extensive interaction network, which includes multiple hydrogen bonds, pi-cation electrostatic interactions, and hydrophobic contacts. The synthesized compounds, though promising, require further structural optimization to improve their interaction profiles and potency.

Evaluation of biological activities

We assessed the cytotoxic activities of the prepared compounds against cysteinyl leukotrienes (CysLT2) antagonists. Notably, Table 3 shows the inhibitory profiles of **4a-j**. Clearly, **4c** and **4g** have superior inhibitory percentages compared to other compounds, prompting us to pursue their IC_{50} values. Fig. 15 shows the resulting dose/response curves and IC_{50} values.

Table 3. Percent inhibition values of CysLT2 at 10 μM concentration of the prepared compounds.

Compound	% Inhibition at 10 μM ^a	IC_{50} (μM)
4a	10	ND ^b
4b	20	ND ^b
4c	14	ND ^b
4d	56	18.7
4e	8	ND ^b
4f	7	ND ^b
4g	54	15.5
4h	5	ND ^b
4i	6	ND ^b
4j	6	ND ^b
11a ^c		$IC_{50} = 2.9 \text{ nM}$

^a Average of duplicate measurements \pm standard deviation,

^b ND: Not determined.

^c Standard inhibitor (Gusach, A. et al. 2019).

Figure 14. Stick representation of **a. 4d** and **b. 4g** docked within the CysLT2 receptor (PDB ID: 6RZ6) binding site. Generated by Biovia Discovery Studio Visualizer[®].

Figure 15. Dose-response curves of compounds **4d** and **4g** CysLT2 antagonist. **A.** Dose-response curve of **4d** with $IC_{50} = 18.7 \mu\text{M}$; **B.** Dose-response curve of **4g** with $IC_{50} = 15.5 \mu\text{M}$.

Conclusion

This study investigates a novel series of compounds featuring benzo[*d*][1,3]dioxol-5-ol as Cysteinyl Leukotriene (CysLT) antagonists. These compounds were synthesized through the direct reaction of 5-(prop-2-yn-1-yloxy) benzo[*d*][1,3]dioxole with various secondary aliphatic amines. In vitro evaluations indicated that, while all compounds displayed weak inhibitory activity against CysLT2, compounds **4d** and **4g** showed notable IC₅₀ values of 18.7 μM and 15.5 μM, respectively.

Molecular docking studies further revealed differences in binding energy and interaction profiles between the synthesized compounds (**4d** and **4g**) and the co-crystallized antagonist (Compound **11a**). Although **4g** exhibited better binding affinity than **4d**, neither matched the binding potency of Compound **11a**. These findings highlight the need for further structural optimization to enhance the binding strength and inhibitory efficacy of the synthesized compounds against the CysLT2 receptor.

Introducing functional groups capable of forming additional hydrogen bonds or electrostatic interactions could significantly improve their binding affinity and potency. This study provides a valuable foundation for the rational design of more potent CysLT2 receptor inhibitors in future research.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

Supplementary data

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Data type: docx

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